

Original Research Article

The Roles of Actors in Performing Classroom Mathematics: Analyzing Student Readings of Euler

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes and reflects upon a classroom experiment in which students first read a passage on the logarithm from Leonhard Euler's *Introductio in Analysin Infinitorum* and then wrote a report. My analysis is framed through ideas derived from the works of Emmanuel Levinas, with particular focus the actors involved in the experiment including: The author of the passage, the teacher, members of the educational institution, and representatives of the mathematical community. With respect to the various actors, fundamental roles are identified: The I (the student), the Other (the author), the Third (the teacher, the members of the institution, and the mathematicians); while acknowledging that the teacher could alternatively cover the role of Other and Third. These roles are illustrated through the analysis of students' reports. I give particular attention to the case of Marta, a student who shows a prevalent reference to the Third Party to the detriment of reference to the Other. I conclude that: (1) The students' choice to report rules functions as reference to the Third Party, and (2) the general invalidity of the proposed formal rule is associated with the deficiency of the I-Other relation. I close with a final reflection concerning the extension of these two conclusions to other situations in the mathematics classroom, namely the discussion and problematization of common practices in the teaching/learning of mathematics alongside critical observations regarding the role of the educational institution.

KEYWORDS: I-Other-Third Party; Levinas; history of mathematics; Euler's passage; students' learning.

About My Experience as a Math Teacher

This article arises out of reflections on my experience as a mathematics teacher in the Italian secondary school system, now retired. Therefore, it offers a different perspective from that of a hegemonic researcher in mathematics education. Compared to a traditional researcher, my experience of almost 40 years provides me with a perspective that axiologically demands attention to the lived complexity of the work in the classroom as experienced firsthand by pedagogues. I recognize that this perspective makes it challenging-nigh-impossible to focus on any singular

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aspect of the dense interconnectedness of reality, and this I position as dialectically simultaneous affordance and constraint. My first aim in writing this article is to distill a line of reasoning abstracted from many elements of everyday life in the classroom, such as the personal knowledge of the students gained over months or even years of working together. I wonder what hidden assumptions might influence my speech—perhaps assumptions regarding the general character of the classroom—hegemonically marginalized by research methodologies that mitigate the complexity of lived reality... or perhaps we might abandon altogether the idea that the lived reality of classrooms is reducible to any such general character.

I have taught in middle school (sixth-eighth grade) and in high school (ninth-thirteenth grade). Up to the tenth grade, Italian school is compulsory; starting from the ninth grade, students must choose the course of study they intend to attend. I have taught in high school for twenty-five years. The aspect that perhaps more than any other has inspired reflections of the sort I share here concerns those situations in which students prioritize the achievement of the goals that the school requires (sufficient grades and promotion) before the search for understanding. I remember my embodied reaction, which I could barely contain, provoked in me by the words of students who, in class dialogue, in the execution of an assignment or in a test, reported statements or procedures that they then could not justify. My subsequent reflections concerned both the behavior of the students and the initiatives of the school, and I questioned myself on my role as a teacher.

During my work in class, I have noticed numerous situations in which students abandon the search for understanding. In cases of cheating, especially in written tests, students act dishonestly for their own advantage. In other situations, students make up for their partial knowledge of a topic by using a succession of steps in a slavish way (Demattè, 2022—this case centers the study of the sign of a fractional rational function). In view of formal summative assessment, some students seem to give up on understanding—resigned to not having understood—made visible when they ask questions like: "In the test, is it true that you don't ask us about this topic?" In this article, I illustrate a case in which a student, Marta, writes a rule that is generally wrong but which she can use to solve some exercises correctly—a rule that guarantees a mathematical performance—and this for the student is already "mission accomplished" regardless of the fact that a more accurate reading would have allowed her to detect why it was wrong. Why did she try to write a general rule? What characteristics does a mathematical rule have when considered as a manifestation of the passage from the student's personal elaboration to the manifestation and sharing of knowledge? I believe that Marta provides an example of those situations that are realized according to this scheme which may be all too familiar for so many mathematics teachers: A subject detects the task required by the institution, produces a performance that satisfies this task, omits the critical review of the performance despite the fact that the cognitive tools for such review are available to the subject.

To be clear, the center of this critique is not students per se. The classroom is a complex ecosystem, and my intent is to sit with that complexity. For example, the teacher himself can play a role in convincing students to put the search for good grades before understanding, e.g. by proposing rules or formulas to students without discussing their validity and subsequently only asking them to apply those rules/formulas to solve exercises. For a more specific example of this general pattern, students using the solution formula for quadratic equations to answer the task "solve the following equations" while remaining unaware of the derivation of this formula or the fact that it allows you to find the zeros of a quadratic polynomial. In view of the administration of the national assessment tests, in which about half of the items consist of multiple-choice questions, I myself suggested that students examine the five alternative answers, discard one or two that appear evidently wrong, and choose one of the others at random (obviously in the case in which

they believe they have not identified the correct answer). Lived reality is rarely reducible to cases of either/or, and oft we bear complicity in systems of (epistemic) oppression even when we also resist those systems.

An initial analysis of these experiences led me to experience resonance with Howard Gardner's "correct answer compromise": If the student affirms a certain thing, teachers and assessors commonly accept that this indicates that learning has occurred without further investigation. This is an idea that I find very enlightening insofar as it explains many of the choices that teachers make in class and also helps to make sense of the attitude of students when they rotely apply rules and formulas that allow them to obtain correct answers. Gardner's idea made me reflect on the fact that the teacher can change the type of question, thus requiring another type of answer, and that this determines a better approximation to what the teacher considers to be actual learning. Furthermore, the idea suggests that learning is a process whose conclusion can never be rendered fully visible: How many questions will the teacher have to ask in order to be able to say that the student has "learned" quadratic equations? The aspect that I consider fundamental—and which is fundamental in the present article, too—is that Gardner's idea concerns the exchange between teacher and students.

The reference only to the mathematical content does not exhaust the analysis of what happens in the classroom. The difficulties in mathematics of many of my students have led me to reflect on their willingness to make a lasting commitment, to dialogue with the teacher and with their peers, to review and refine their ideas, and so forth. I have reflected on the role of the student in relation to the teacher. I have also become aware of the fact that the school institution has a role that goes beyond logistics, that is, the organization of the structure in which the class is located. This role is not reducible to something purely positive or purely negative, thus justifying—or even demanding—a critical approach to the analysis of the mathematics class. The encounter with the thought of French Lithuanian philosopher Emmanuel Levinas (1906-1995) has opened new horizons for me regarding the role of human beings who interact in the classroom. Now I believe that the most productive approach is one which centers ethics: "Ethics as first philosophy" (Levinas, 1989).

Introduction

This section is organized as follows: (1) an introduction to some aspects of Levinas' thought, (2) the description of a classroom experience regarding the use of a historical document, and then (3) the discussion of general aspects concerning mathematics education.

I recognize that the coexistence of Philosophy-History-Mathematics Education can make reading complex. If the reader were a philosopher, he might find the references to Levinas's thought with "mathematics education in mind" naive on the one hand, and perhaps inappropriate on the other. If the reader were a historian of mathematics, he might, for example, detect the lack of an analysis with students of the contextualization of the excerpt within Euler's work from which it is taken (*Introductio in Analysin Infinitorum*) or with reference to the original written in Latin. The disciplinary core of this paper is instead mathematical education, but with the understanding that philosophy and history are part of the constituent substance of our discipline: I mention other authors who have referred to Levinas's thought in the context of mathematical education; I highlight the pedagogical aspects of the use of Euler's excerpt, with awareness that a full historical analysis would be functionally impossible within the limits of the resources and constraints of the institution of schooling (e.g. number of hours available and needs of the students).

Levinas offers conceptual tools with which we can analyze the classroom experience and its outcomes. In particular, I leverage theoretical aspects of Levinas' thought to describe pertinent characteristics of the work produced by the student Marta, surfacing a distinction between what an individual might produce in their personal (private) construction of mathematical thought contra what they might create to share with a larger community based on their perception of the desires/values of that community. In this sense, the purpose I ascribe to this article is to re-propose the importance of Levinas' thought for mathematical education from the perspective of a career practitioner, recalling that other authors have spoken about it specifically within a discourse that concerns postmodern philosophy.

More specifically, I use theories derived from Levinas to pose a reflection on a student's relations with other people, and on the consequences with respect to learning in the mathematics class considered within the educational institution. The roles of the teacher, of the author of the passage that the students read, and of the members of the institution and scientific community are mentioned. I consider how various people can play different roles with respect to the student. Referring to the relations between subjects, Levinas recovers the roots of ethics in human subjectivity, and not in an *a priori* defined code (see Maheux et al., 2010).

Walsh (Ed., 2004) reconsiders mathematics education from a postmodern perspective with reference to authors such as Lacan, Foucault, and Levinas. In particular, Foucault's analysis of knowledge and power is mentioned: He shows how knowledge implies forms of social organization and constitutes individuals as thinking, feeling and acting subjects (p.4). In Chapter 4, Neyland (2004) points out that a postmodern orientation in mathematics education guides teachers toward goals of high standards, but "it is based on the conviction that the modern way of attempting to achieve these ends is both undesirable and illusory" (p.56); from this postmodern perspective, human experience involves "a growing pluralism of authority" (p.58). Neylan (2004) insists on Emmanuel Levinas as the source of a postmodern alternative to "[t]he modernist ethical orientation" (p.56).

For a discussion on "(Re)Constructing the Heart of Mathematics Education", Bowers et al. (2024) take up the thought of Levinas and his Ethics as first philosophy (Levinas, 1989). They develop the idea of a refoundation of Western philosophy on ethics. This is a subversion that questions those who deal with mathematics education and problematizes much work in the classroom and in research. In Levinas' ethics, the theme of responsibility between people is central.

Regarding the references to Levinas' work made in this article, problems arise about fidelity to his work considering that my aim is to analyze what happens in the mathematics classroom. Zhao (2016) notes that Levinas has not written extensively on education. Despite this, his philosophy gives the conceptual tools with which we can rethink educational theory and practice in radically new ways. The Levinas scholarship in education developed "from an earlier cautious exposition and concern for faithful interpretation to the later more full-blown, critical analysis and creative extension of his ideas". She moreover highlights that Levinas' philosophy "hinges on a disruption of Being and Presence and on the claim of the impossibility of thematization, and his writing is enigmatic and at times elusive". I believe that these aspects of Levinas' thought can fuel ongoing reflection in mathematics education, providing the tools for a critical analysis of what happens in the classroom, and with respect to students as human subjects.

I would like to underline that the focus of the present article is on the relations between people engaged with mathematical content and not, *stricto sensu*, on responsibility for the content: I do not intend to linger on the ethics dealing with non-human inanimate objects discussed, for example, by Nelson (2020). When in (Demattè, 2022b) I speak of "student's ethical relation with a mathematical written text," I mean to refer in abbreviated form to the numerous relations between

people that the text embodies—with the author but also with other possibly cited authors, with the author of any premise or introduction, with the teacher themselves when they are involved in the interpretation together with the students and can influence them, etc.

Educational institutions include preschools, childcare, primary-elementary schools, secondary-high schools, colleges, and universities. As Durkheim (1982, p. 54) states, schools respond to the demands of the "social environment" of which teachers are "representatives and intermediaries". The reference to school-as-institution in the present article is intended to underline a substantial, possible mystification which consists in attributing the outcomes of students' work exclusively to the interaction between students and teachers. Thanks to the Levinas' thought, we can consider who does not have an immediately visible role with respect to the students but to whom it is possible to ascribe some outcomes of students' work nonetheless.

Theoretical Frame

Abtahi (2018, pp. 1-2) underlines the role of the other "as anything that carries within it the social, cultural and historical vestiges of its formation, use, modifications, becoming and being." She refers to the other in order to reflect on the combination of the theoretical ideas of Piaget and Vygotsky, thereby placing her analysis within a debate that covered much of the twentieth century. She argues that in a Vygotskian approach, individual learning depends on the organizational features of the social interaction. She moreover points out that in Piaget "others also play a role – not necessarily in the process of cognitive change (i.e., learning) but instead in the assessment of the viability of the end product (i.e., the newly formed concept or activity)." (p. 8) In the present article, the focus is the other considered as an actor/person/human subject in the students' learning process. A role exists for all representatives of the social environment who organize the possibility of interaction—so that this process occurs—and who set criteria according to which individual learning can be considered to have occurred.

According to Radford (2023), mathematics teaching-learning is an ethical event "based on relations with others." He poses several types of "relations between people": "relations of power and subjection, relations of authority and obedience, and relations of solidarity and inclusiveness." (p. 187) Radford highlights how mathematics in the classroom, a particular form of knowledge, is subject to legitimation. The present article concerns how students approach the need to produce mathematics according to certain criteria—which they may have consciously or only tacitly grasped in their experience during their years at school. In this way, by referring to "third" parties not directly present in class but who inform or construct the criteria on the basis of which the students' mathematical production is assessed.

According to Freire (2000, p. 84), the term *process* in reference to teaching and learning indicates unfolding over time. Education is a "process of becoming" and an "ongoing activity".

In the classroom, in front of a mathematical proposal, of something new to them, students are first of all called to accept it, often passively, face-to-face with a disciplinary path whose development they are not aware of, which they are expected to "know" just by internalizing the proposal. It is an act of entrustment to the teacher. I maintain that this not only applies to transmissive lectures but also, for example, to collaborative learning classes—in "a communitarian relational ethics" (Radford, 2021).

The institution gives the mathematics teacher, with whom the students meet repeatedly across a span of time, the mandate to make working proposals to the students with attention towards learning mathematics. I argue that the student does not find in the teacher only a representative of the institution: In mathematics teaching-learning, there is another type of relation between the student and the teacher. The teacher represents the institution in creating the conditions for

learning to take place and, moreover, participates in students' learning by engaging in dialogue with them; that is, with respect to the students, the teacher can play the role of the Third and of the Other (capitalized, to mean that an ethical relation has been established).

Levinasian Relation with the Other, and Mathematics Class

In this subsection I surface some relevant aspects of Levinas' thought, chosen with consideration of the subjects involved in educational institutions. The fact that Levinas never made direct reference to mathematics education necessitates a discussion in which relevant aspects of his thought are systematically highlighted as inspiring and organizing reasons for subsequent reflection on the specific themes of mathematics education discussed in this article.

Levinas has been a source of inspiration for various contributions to education. Joldersma (2014) considers education's commonplaces—teaching, learning, curriculum, institutions—and elucidates the role of responsibility and justice. Guillemette (2018) and Demattè (2022b) discuss Levinas' contributions to otherness in mathematics education, underlining the relevance of using history and original documents in teaching-learning, and highlighting some ideas of Levinas which can help us reflect on students' experience in the classroom, on their work in relation with subjects who are face-to-face with them or other ones whose presence is mediated by texts or by various didactical materials or other connections. These ethical relations can be seen as opportunities for learning to listen to the other (see Arcavi & Isoda, 2007).

The I-Other relation and constituent responsibility for the Other is the origin of ethics. Note that this is not a generic other—the use of capital O is precisely due to the fact that an ethical relation has been established. This relation is “asymmetrical” (Levinas, 1979, p. 215). With reference to mathematics education, this recalls the role of the teacher who makes a mathematical proposal to the students (and therefore operates in his institutional role), with this asymmetrical ethical relation requiring responsiveness to student's needs. Within the teaching-learning process, the teacher orients their choices around this responsibility, consciously but also unconsciously.

Student learning can also take place through written texts. In this interaction, the student metaphorically meets the author and enters in dialogue: An ethical relation is established. Regarding interpretation, aligning with Gadamer (2006, p.362), I consider “hermeneutic as entering into dialogue with the text.” This dialogue is embodied in acts such as the reader posing questions and searching for answers. When the teacher assumes the role of Other of the Student (the I), both thematise the same mathematical content as an opportunity to divert from thematizing the relation with the interlocutor—they share a discourse in which everybody signifies something to the Other. Arguing that class work has to be based on dialogue, I make reference to the “dialogical/ethical perspective” by Guillemette & Radford (2022, p.1500). Focusing on classroom talk, Drageset & Ell (2024) insist on talk moves, teacher interactions, and discourse patterns in mathematics education.

Through a text, the author illustrates his own thoughts and can be a guide for the student but, in the meantime, they exposes themselves to the possibility of error, or subjection to criticism—see, for example, the equalities reported by Euler (1748, par. 99) “ $a^z=0^{-3}=1/0^3=1/0$ ”: He is in a position of weakness. The students live their own weakness because of their possible or perceived unworthiness with respect to some aspects of the text they are interpreting, and with respect to the community of knowledge from which it arose (e.g. mathematicians).

With respect to the study of a text, a relation of answerability can be established. It non-exhaustively comprises adherence to at least some aspects of the text, and propensity to use personal resources and to reflect critically on themselves— “The self-criticism can be understood as a discovery of one's weakness or a discovery of one's unworthiness” (Levinas, 1979, p. 83). In this ethical relationship, students have a responsibility follow the details of author's proposal, agree

to review their own preconceptions, and strive to not make a distorted use of the text through mnemonic study. I don't consider as "responsible" the students who, inspired by the proposal of the author, abandon author's reasoning² to develop their own—this is, in effect, a refusal of that ethical relationship. Regarding the fundamental concept of responsibility, see Levinas (1991, for instance, pp. 9 and following).

Note that—as reported in (Demattè, 2022b)—even if the I-Other relation is established, students' elaboration of the text may contain mathematical errors like in the case of Gaia, or may be correct like in Francesca. The I-Other relation does not guarantee that learning occurs and there remains a reasonable doubt whether this relation could have produced acceptable results from the point of view of mathematical thinking. Results are shaped by the specificity of students' subjectivity, and even by many contingent elements such as misunderstandings or trivial errors. Mathematics content has to be manifested respecting certain criteria in order to be effectively communicated. I am reminded of the value attributed to the communication of mathematical knowledge in Sfard's *commognition* (Sfard, 2021). The manifested content is exposed to a possible judgment, made via the teacher, per the values of the mathematical community which is composed of mathematical insiders—"a group including mathematicians, mathematics educators, mathematics teachers, mathematics-related professionals and others who have specialised in mathematics" (Ernest, 2019).

Other authors have a different approach to the relations in the classroom. Mason (1994) proposes an "I-You relationship". He refers to Buber (1970), a philosopher to whom Levinas himself refers for developing some reflections. According to Levinas, it is difficult to think of such a relationship, as it appears closed and self-sufficient, differently of the I-Other relation. With reference to the mathematics classroom, this relation might better describe the situation in which the students are called to face proposals made by the teacher in their alterity—not always in line with student interests. Yet, even in this situation, the shadow of a third party hangs over proceedings, as the values by which proposals and responses are judged arise out of neither the teacher nor the student per se, but instead out of the values of a larger community of practice.

The Third Party: The Far

Bakhtin (1986, p.126) states that:

[A]ny utterance always has an addressee (of various sorts, with varying degrees of proximity, concreteness, awareness, and so forth), whose responsive understanding the author of the speech work seeks and surpasses. This is the second party [...]. But in addition to this addressee (the second party), the author of the utterance, with a greater or lesser awareness, presupposes a higher superaddressee (third), whose absolutely just responsive understanding is presumed, either in some metaphysical distance or in distant historical time (the loophole addressee). In various ages and with various understandings of the world, this superaddressee and his ideally true responsive understanding assume various ideological expressions (God, absolute truth, the court of dispassionate human conscience, the people, the court of history, science, and so forth).

In this passage, Bakhtin refers to what Levinas calls "the Other" using the expression "the second party". The concept of "superaddressee", as exemplified in parentheses by Bakhtin at the end of the quote, refers to people, but not only. In mathematics, as in the case of science, the people who over the centuries have built the body of knowledge called 'mathematics' comprise

² I agree with Kolloche (2021) about what is meant by "mathematical reasoning," i.e. assertions and discourse aimed at mathematical justification. This can help to frame the student work I analyze later in this article.

one such human (but not just) superaddressee. In all this, I see a fundamental connection between what Bakhtin and Levinas say.

According to Levinas, the I-Other relation does not exclude the establishment of other ethical relations. This leads to considering a Third Party understood, in particular, as a neighbor of the Other. “The third party is other than the neighbor, but also another neighbor, and also a neighbor of the other” (Levinas 1991, p.157). One might have expected Levinas to use the expression “Other of the Other”: the term “neighbor” suggests that the relationship with the Other may not have been established—i.e. it is a proximity not otherwise defined.

The Third challenges individual ethical relations, problematizing them. Simmons (1999, p. 83) illustrates how “Levinas moves from the anarchical, ethical relationship with the Other to the totalizing realm of politics with his phenomenology of the third person, the Third.” As Levinas (1979, p. 213) says, “The third party looks at me in the eyes of the Other”—a suggestive image which can recall the complex role of the author of the text as Other (or of the teacher, in case we would like to focus their role). I consider as Other of the author some of members of the mathematical community, existing in ethical relation with the author. This is not a relation trivially reducible to a relation between individuals. I consider mathematical community to be the set of people in ethical relations while dealing with mathematics.

Levinas refers to the "Third Party" at various points in his works, mainly in (Levinas, 1991). As highlighted by Ricoeur (2004), Levinas returns to the concept repeatedly, without enucleating a concise definition. I argue that analysis of a student's beliefs (affective factors included)—see (Furinghetti & Pehkonen, 2002)—can find its origin in those relations, thus influencing cognition and behavior.

The whole theoretical discussion of the Third Party revolves around the key word "justice." Justice is "comparison, coexistence, contemporaneity, assembling, order, thematization" (Levinas, 1991, p. 157). In the I-Other relation, there is only a "latent birth of knowledge" (Levinas, 1979, p. 157)—that which in the students is vague and in progress must be focused, ordered, and reassembled according to criteria shared by competent persons. Restated with an emphasis on the temporal aspect and with reference to language, the Third Party requires "a synchronization of terms, a recourse to systematic language, a constant use of the verb *to be*" (Levinas, 1991, p. 155, emphasis added). Ultimately, mathematical knowledge exchanged in the I-Other relation must be conveyed using the language of mathematics since this shared language makes it possible for the members of the community to understand each other. Regarding time and synchronization, de Saussure (1959, p. 81) states that “Everything that relates to the static side of our science is synchronic; everything that has to do with evolution is diachronic. Similarly, synchrony and diachrony designate respectively a language-state and an evolutionary phase.” The use of the verb *to be* in the present attests to the achievement of a static side. Levinas (1987) returns to time, ethics, encounter with the other, and sociality. For a more direct reference to mathematics learning, see (Guillemette & Radford, 2022).

The Third considered here is the community of mathematicians, bearers of knowledge built up over the centuries through relations between other human subjects. The teacher belongs to the mathematical community (as the students themselves recognize when, as an alternative to teacher's name, they say "the mathematics teacher"), as does the author of the text the students are reading. What happens is that the ethical relation I-Other subverts that role as a Third. In any case, the students refer to a Third (the community of mathematicians which remains in its role as Third Party) regarding “guidelines” of doing mathematics, for instance: reasonings are required, the truth of the statements is crucial, natural language is a resource, it is convenient to use a certain

formalism, formal writings show properties of mathematical objects and procedures, and so forth (see also van Oers, 2001).

There is a widespread practice in class work: carrying out exercises. I define what I mean by "exercise" through reference to the definition of "problem" borrowed from psychological studies and reported, for example, by Mayer (1985) or Schoenfeld (1985). In a problem we can identify a given state, a goal state, and a no obvious way of accomplishing that goal. In an exercise, on the contrary, that way is substantially obvious. I consider exercises as generic examples of other possible exercises—borrowing the Mason & Pimm (1984) idea of “generic examples”—and therefore they are resources for the students called to face similar exercises on tests. Exercises contrast with—recalling Levinas (1979b, p. 27)—the persistence in itself of the thought of the students to which is attributed the idea of containing being. In fact, through the request to face a *surplus of being* (various situations etc.), exercises distract students from an act of presumption—to get them out of a feeling of self-sufficiency—by proposing other aspects of being in which their previous acquisitions must integrate (see Demattè, 2022a). In administering exercises, the teacher orients students' gaze toward a Third Party, in view of a future test or high-stakes assessment. For the next part of this article, I would like to underline that reference to summative assessments seems for students a polarizing aspect of schooling, and assessment practices have a large impact on learning process. This combines with the fact that school mathematics largely represents a culture of *compliance* (see Juuso & Päivi, 2023), giving rise to or exacerbating negative consequences. All this will be problematized here.

Summing up, the passage from the I-Other relation—still in a certain way a private fact—to the relation with a Third Party is a crucial phase. I argue that this relation is in itself—like the I-Other relation—a necessary stage for students. I will illustrate and analyse it through the outcomes of an experiment. For this purpose, I will refer primarily to one student's writing but briefly mention the content of other students' writings.

Historical Sources for Research in Mathematics Education

Chorlay *et al.* (2022) offer an overview of research on the significance and relevance of the history of mathematics in the context of mathematics education. Recently, this field has evolved into a domain of educational research and practice, raising relevant theoretical issues concerning mathematics teaching and learning. In the domain of History and Pedagogy of Mathematics, particular attention has been dedicated to “original historical sources and their educational effects: classroom implementations, enhancing and deepening reflections on the teaching and learning of mathematics” (Chorlay *et al.*, 2022, p.1411), underlining the importance of *empirical investigations* (italics in the original).

Aligning with philosophical hermeneutics, I consider that the students, as interpreters, compare their own pre-knowledge with what a text reports. Gadamer (2006) uses the language of "prejudice"/"fore conception"/"pre-understanding" (*Vorverständnisse*). In the present article, with these terms I refer both to a specific mathematical content (for example: "the logarithm of a number is the exponent...") and to the management of that content—metacognitive aspects—e.g. strategic selection of heuristics (Schoenfeld, 1985).

Objectives of the Class Experiment

The present article is part of a research project concerning the use of original historical sources in upper secondary school. The underlying research questions concern the origin of what Guillemette (2017) describes as "empathy from students towards the authors" of historical texts. Demattè (2019) surfaces how the author of a text can leave involuntary traces that recall him, even

characterize him: the way of exposing a mathematical reasoning, the use or not of a symbolism, the reference to situations of everyday life, etc. —characteristics that refer to a human being and help to situate their work in a cultural and personal context. Subsequent works (Demattè, 2021; Guillemette & Demattè, 2022) discuss the use of historical originals in the classroom with reference to the thought of Levinas, specifically to the ethical relation I-Other between student and author of the text. Students' interpretations refer to the Other by establishing an ethical relation of responsibility when they show "attention, interest, participation in the analysis work, search for sharing mathematical reasoning," and if they "if they seek to consolidate the links between the author's reasoning and their own" (Demattè, 2022b). In some cases, the students produce a written report but do not establish the ethical relation. Questions then arise with respect to the research questions of this article:

In the interpretation of a mathematical text—without a student's relation of responsibility with the Other—how is the students' written production characterized? Is there a relation between human beings that can be described through the relations illustrated by Levinas? Does this connect to a relation with a Third Party?

In the experiment described in the following pages, I consider the teacher in the role of a Third Party (one of the two roles he can play in mathematics classroom), because he introduced the students work. I also consider the teacher's Others—the mathematical community that looked at the student through the eyes of the teacher, I suppose, during the years of student's stay at school.

The experiment is inherent to students' learning, analysed through one of their mathematical tasks (see also Simon *et al.*, 2010). The reference, for research, to a student's writing suggests specific points of attention and cautions in inferring conclusions, considering: the transcendence of the individual students as human beings (it must be stated with caution that their thoughts are being investigated), and the fact that in the experiment the writing is requested by the teacher who represents the institution (a particular product, and not an informal exchange, e.g. not by somebody outside the institution).

Method: A Historical Source and the Work with Students

The experiment took place in a class of the thirteenth grade (18-19 years old students) of an Italian upper secondary school. In the previous twelfth grade, alongside traditional activities, students attended activities linked to the history of mathematics. The class dealt with the interpretation of historical passages (primary and secondary sources) under the guidance of the teacher, and faced exercises and problems taken from Euler's works concerning the concepts of exponential and logarithm: from *Introductio in analysin infinitorum* (Euler, 1748a) and from *Vollständige Anleitung zur Algebra* (Euler, 1765). These activities were not aimed at setting up an organic historical discourse nor at reflecting on the history of mathematics per se, but at creating the conditions for a direct involvement of the student vis-à-vis building mathematical knowledge as outcome of teaching-learning process.

As shown in educational research, the concept of logarithm commonly entails various types of difficulties in students (see, for example, Dintarini, 2018). As the teacher of the class in which the experiment was carried out, I noticed that some students did not know how to explain the link between exponential and logarithmic, that most of them were not able to say why the logarithm function increases in the case of base greater than 1 and decreases with base between 0 and 1, that many were unable to reason about the sign of the logarithm function, that many mistakenly remembered the (pseudo)fact that the logarithm function could not assume negative values. These difficulties motivated the use of some mathematical activities with students, among which was the one described in the present article. This activity employed the Euler's passage shown in *Fig. 1*. Immediately after resuming in class the concepts of exponential and logarithm, I provided students

with the passage as a component of an individual homework assignment. They were asked to write their interpretation—about “reading-writing” as a “paired language art” see (Yore & Tang, 2022)—starting from the instruction “Write everything you can say about Euler’s text,” with the clarification that there would be attributed neither judgments nor marks. The instruction was intentionally open-ended, in order not to influence their choices about what to thematize in their writings. The students were required to send their works to me by email. Two of the 21 members of the class did not deliver their works.

“103. Whatever logarithmic base we choose, we always have $\log 1 = 0$, since in the equation $a^z = y$, which corresponds to $z = \log y$, when we let $y = 1$ we have $z = 0$. From this it follows that the logarithm of a number greater than 1 will be positive, depending on the base a . Thus, $\log a = 1$, $\log a^2 = 2$, $\log a^3 = 3$, $\log a^4 = 4$, etc. and, after the fact, we know what base has been chosen, that is the number whose logarithm is equal to 1 is the logarithmic base. The logarithm of a positive number less than 1 will be negative. Notice that $\log \frac{1}{a} = -1$, $\log \frac{1}{a^2} = -2$, $\log \frac{1}{a^3} = -3$, etc., but the logarithms of negative numbers will not be real, but complex, as we have already noted”.

Leonhard Euler, *Introductio in analysin infinitorum*;
translation by J.D. Blanton (Euler, 1988, p. 79).

Fig. 1. Euler’s passage provided to the students.

In the original text, Euler uses the term “*imaginarius*” (imaginary) in contrast with “*realis*” (real). Blanton translates “*imaginarius*” with “complex”; Bruce (1748b, pp. 155-156) translates it with “imaginary”. In the passage, Euler uses $1/a$ to represent a number less than 1, being the base a is greater than 1, as it is possible to infer from the third line of the passage (“the logarithm of a number greater than 1 will be positive”). In the second and third line of the passage, we can also note the logical connector “From this it follows...”. Euler’s inference is justified in paragraph 98, where he says that in case the base is greater than 1, a^z will have a greater value if the value of z is greater (Fig. 2).

**si enim fuerit $a > 1$, tum valor ipsius a^z eo erunt majores,
quo major numerus loco z substituatur**

Fig. 2. From Euler (1748a, paragraph 98).

Considering the preservation of monotonicity by the inverse function, it is justified that from $\log 1 = 0$ it follows that the logarithm of a number greater than 1 will be positive.

With respect to the research objectives of this experiment, it was important to detect points on which the students chose to linger, to detect whether they chose to rework them by changing exposition—e.g. by using words instead of symbols or vice-versa—or if they chose to use them as a starting point for structuring their personal mathematical reasoning. The use of passages (including the one in Fig.1) from Euler’s *Introductio in analysin infinitorum* arose out of prior experience, as I had previously experimented with them in a laboratory setting as described by Demattè & Furinghetti (2014).

About three months after the text interpretation activity, I briefly interviewed almost all the students, individually, outside the classroom in which the others were engaged in a lesson concerning another school subject. They were asked one or more oral questions derived from the analysis of their individual works, and their answers were transcribed. At the end, the students

could check if what was written faithfully reflected what they intended to say and pose changes or additions.

Marta's Writing

Among the students who took part in the experiment, the present article focuses on Marta³. Therefore, this paper incorporates some features of *case study* insofar as it is an application of general philosophical investigations to a concrete and specific example. From the point of view illustrated by Smedslund (2009), this study exists at the interstice between phenomenon and research: it was born from a teacher's efforts—my efforts—to meet the needs of a secondary school class in northern Italy, with analysis informed by a set of voices from philosophical and mathematical research. These philosophical and mathematical perspectives are leveraged to support my and others ongoing development as teachers to similar classes.

Marta's school biography, as expressed through hegemonic framing, is one that I suspect will be familiar to all teachers in relatively conventional institutions of schooling: a low-achieving student, with long-standing difficulties in mathematics and science in general, with test scores in most cases below the acceptable threshold. This hegemonic framing displaces systemic nuance with individualism, but it is pertinent to mention it here insofar as it illustrates the tension that exists betwixt institution and individual for students like Marta. I believe that Marta shows, and in some ways accentuates, the characteristics of students who, like her, experience systemic challenges in mathematics and seek a solution in their relationship with mathematics or schooling as institution. My decision to focus on her work among the 19 produced by the students of the class was motivated by the clarity with which her predominant reference to the Third emerges.

In *Fig. 3*, the work written by Marta is reported⁴.

In this document the exponent, therefore the logarithm of the equation is “z”. ($y = 1$ then $z = 0$)
 In later passages it is shown that logarithms are the same as exponents of various numbers; a logarithm can be negative when the exponent it corresponds to is in the denominator instead of the nominator [*sic*].
 It was difficult for me to understand the document, but I managed to extract some basic rules, such as:

- The logarithm can be negative when the exponent is in the denominator
- The logarithm of a number is its exponent or an exponent that can help us get to the number we need

Fig. 3. *Marta's writing.*

In her writing, Marta begins by incompletely reporting the reasoning set out in the first two lines of Euler's text. In the next part, she writes two propositions twice, in slightly different forms: one concerning the definition of the logarithm, the other concerning the case in which the logarithm is negative. She then reports a personal reworking of what Euler discusses. In a notable portion of her writing, she talks about herself and her difficulty in understanding the text. Therefore, her work can be divided into three parts, as shown in *Fig. 4*.

³ All student names in this article are pseudonyms

⁴ The formatting of her file is preserved, apart from the type of font.

- a) Relation with the Other; adherence to Euler's reasoning ("In this document the exponent, therefore the logarithm of the equation is "z", ($y=1$ then $z=0$)");
- b) Reference to the I/herself ("It was difficult for me to understand the document, but I managed to extract [rules]");
- c) Relation with the Third Party; rules that Marta considers useful for solving exercises (as it results from her interview) - the predominant part in her short work ("In later passages it is shown that logarithms are the same as exponents of various numbers; a logarithm can be negative when the exponent it corresponds to is in the denominator instead of the nominator. [...] some basic rules, such as: • The logarithm can be negative when the exponent is in the denominator • The logarithm of a number is its exponent or an exponent that can help us get to the number we need").

Fig. 4. Schematization of Marta's writing.

Faced with the request "write everything you can say about Euler's passage," all students wrote about mathematics, even though it was not explicitly requested. Similarities with Marta's work emerge from that of her classmates. Some of the students refer to "rules" or "formulas" relating to the specifics of Euler's passage and to mathematics in general. For example:

- Doris writes that "mathematics is a concept [*sic*] to be understood through the practice of exercises and formulas"
- Caterina writes, among other things, a paragraph entitled "Formulas and mathematical synthesis"
- Emanuela produces a scheme with concise statements and symbolic writings.
- Michele reports a reformulation of the content also through personal expressions, such as the following: "The logarithm of a number is its exponent or the 'ideal' exponent that would be needed to reach the number at the right of equal".
- Corinna writes incorrect statements such as: "The logarithm of a number is always positive when the base is greater than 1", "The logarithm of a number is negative when the base is less than 1".

I share these examples to illustrate that each of these works contains some elements of interest, and to illustrate the existence of nontrivial overlap between the various works. However, for the purposes of the research set out in this article, I choose to focus on the analysis of the text made by Marta for the reason put forth previously.

Discussion on Marta's Writing

I would like to underline that Marta's references to different actors (the Other, The Third Party and, moreover, the I) are the object of analysis, while her difficulties with the concept of logarithm are not (neither their possible origins, nor the possible remedies).

A Third Party in Marta's Writing

In my schematization of Marta's writing (Fig. 4), category C refers to the role of the Third Party. Marta treats the short passage in which Euler speaks of the negative logarithm as the object of her *thematizing thought*⁵ (i.e., she addresses it, so that it can then enter a process described in the following lines). She reports it and chooses the discursive form as her mode of *exposition* (without using mathematical symbols). Her effort seems to be that of trying to give *visibility* to the content of the text so that it is made shareable with others: her writing becomes a way to give *clarity* to at

⁵ In this paragraph, relevant terms are expressed in italics using the language that Levinas (1991) uses in paragraph 3 "From saying to the said or the wisdom of desire" of the fifth chapter "Subjectivity and infinity".

least some aspects of the Euler's passage, which she finds to be difficult; in this way, Marta expresses an opinion that regards the whole text as a gestalt. What Gadamer (2006, p. 294) calls "fore-conception of completeness" seems to emerge, which refers to the fact that "only what really constitutes a unity of meaning is intelligible." In the case of Marta, it seems this might have played a negative role in her learning insofar as it may have discouraged her away from analysing specific pieces of the text, diluting her attention from the specific points in Euler's passage. The *saying*⁶ (writing, without being forced to choose a specific disciplinary aspect) required in the open ended formulation of the task gives rise to Marta's *said*—her way of seeing clearly and tackling the problem she has set herself, namely, to deal with the exercises that have always been central to her work in mathematics (see below her answer when she is interviewed). Through her statements, she exposes herself to a possibility of judgment. She derives a formal property from the passage, giving general validity to the examples regarding powers, which are still particular examples concerning the logarithm of numbers less than 1 despite Euler having expressed them with the use of letters, that is " $\log \frac{1}{a} = -1, \log \frac{1}{a^2} = -2, \log \frac{1}{a^3} = -3, \text{ etc.}$ " Moreover, in Marta's writing I note a part concerning a sort of definition of the logarithm—"logarithms are the same as exponents of various numbers"—which is first reported before her statement on the negative logarithm, though in the bulleted list of Fig. 3 it is reported after, i.e. when she has already examined the role of the exponents which at that point has assumed visibility.

We can find a very small part in Marta's writing—part A in Fig. 4—in which she makes explicit the establishment of the I-Other relation with Euler, the author of the passage. She constructs a relation of *answerability* through the production of the writing and through citing fragments of the text. However, her writing does not show a relation of *responsibility* for the Other, i.e. participation in Euler's reasoning (see Demattè, 2022b). What Marta derives from the passage appears aimed at school assignments: it is not the reasoning proposed by the author that is focused on, but the idea that it can serve towards the achievement of an external purpose (namely, performance on school assessments).

In part B, Marta talks about herself (the I) and refers to one of the actors of the I-Other relation. The relation is in this way thematized, and thus does not remain primigenial but is instead subject to reflection: it is an approach in line with that consequent to the entry of the Third.

In summary, Marta produced a "rule-oriented" script that enabled her to solve a range of exercises. One of these "rules" is purely formal and can be subject to criticism from the point of view of mathematical rigour. Note that Marta omitted to mention the point where Euler says that "the logarithm of a positive number *less than 1* will be negative" (italics added). The analysis of her writing leads to highlighting shortcomings in the I-Other (Student-Author) relation and her orientation to refer to the Third.

In the interview, Marta was asked why she considered the rules she wrote useful. She replied that "the rules are useful for solving the exercises in a simpler way, with less difficulty". The fact that Marta reported negative values for the logarithm was significant, as she was among the students who erroneously remembered that the logarithm cannot be negative. Nevertheless, a doubt arose regarding the eventuality that she considered the fact that the exponent is in the denominator for the logarithm to be negative as a necessary and sufficient condition, or that she

⁶ Levinas (1979, p. 204) points out that "language is not enacted within a consciousness" and that "the essence of language is the relation with the Other" (Levinas, 1979, p. 207). Chapter 1 of Levinas (1991) includes a paragraph entitled "The said and the saying". "The *saying* is antecedent to the linguistic systems" (Levinas, 1991, p. 5). "The subordination of the saying to the said, to the linguistic system and to ontology, is the price that manifestation demands" (Levinas, 1991, p. 6). The "saying" refers to the ethical relation and responsibility to the Other, while the "said" refers to thematized, objective knowledge or discourse.

considered it only necessary, or only sufficient. In class work—after the interpretation of Euler's passage, both before and after the interview—Marta did not show any further criteria at her disposal to find out if a logarithm has a negative value, apart from the "rule" she wrote. She did not explain her orientation in terms of necessary and sufficient conditions, or equivalent, but she solved some exercises correctly and others incorrectly, always in line with her "rule".

When Marta was questioned, examples were presented to her by the teacher. She correctly established the sign of $\log_{10} \frac{1}{10^5}$ and $\log_{10} \frac{1}{100}$; in the latter case, she used the second of her "rules," specifically the second part where she writes that the logarithm of a number is "an exponent that can help us reach the number we need," referring to the fact that $100=10^2$. She was also able to establish the sign of $\log_3 3^4$ and of $\log_2 8$. She was then asked to address examples in which: (A) the exponent is in the denominator but the value of the logarithm is not negative, and examples in which (B) the exponent is in the numerator and the logarithm is negative. Concerning case (A), she erroneously established that the value of $\log_{10} \frac{1}{10^{-3}}$ and $\log_{10} \frac{10}{10^1}$ is negative. Concerning case (B), she considered positive the value of $\log_{10} \frac{1^{10}}{10}$; with help she was able to calculate $\log_{2,5} \frac{2^2}{25}$.

Marta and Third Party: A Problematization

In the previous subsection, I highlighted the characteristics of Marta's writing for which I could say that her reference is to the Third Party, i.e. to the community of mathematicians. However, it is possible for others to occupy the role of Third Party. When Marta says that the rules are useful for solving the exercises in a simpler way, Marta herself seems to suggest this. In fact, mathematical exercises have always been part of the tests she has faced during all her years of secondary school. Passing these tests is, for her, necessary to move on to the next grade and to complete secondary school. Marta seems to suggest that for her the Third Party is the school institution rather than the community of mathematicians.

How can one describe the insertion of a student like her into the school institution from the point of view of the sociology of knowledge? Anyon (1980) speaks of "[r]elationships between [p]eople" and in particular of "relation one has to authority and control at work and in society". Here, the Anyon speaks of authority at work, and refers to individuals within an institution. It is therefore not a question of the authority that is established between individuals from which Levinas derives from the asymmetry of the I-Other relation. On the part of the students with respect to the school institution there seems to be a type of relationship that Anyon describes: "[C]haracteristic of most working-class jobs is that there is no built-in mechanism by which the worker can control the content, process, or speed of work", "work that is routine and mechanical." Considering this as an analogy between school and working-class labor, we find elements to further analyze what Marta has written and stated orally: a) she has a deficient relationship with the other (Euler), b) makes reference to an institution made up of individuals far from her actual learning process, c) the institution requires performances from her, d) her understanding is inadequate to fuel the desired performances, and e) it is advantageous to mechanically express these performances such that understanding them becomes unnecessary vis-à-vis performance.

Another point of view refers directly to mathematics and leads to an explanation for why Marta may be oriented to seek shortcuts towards the performances that the school institution requires of her. I refer to what Skemp (1978, p. 12) calls "instrumental understanding" (versus "relational understanding") in which application of rules has a fundamental role. Skemp, as "Devil's Advocate," states that "instrumental mathematics is usually easier to understand" because "less knowledge is involved [...] the rewards are more immediate, and more apparent" and "one can often get the right answer more quickly and reliably." This recalls the case of Marta: I consider that

she aims at a mathematics that is a tool to achieve instrumentalist purposes other than learning per se (and not even concerning mathematics). From this point of view, it became quite rational that she does not consider all portions of knowledge that she could have obtained from Euler's text, as total understanding was not necessary for her to derive an approach that quickly obtains the correct answer to many of the exercises that had been proposed to her.

As a teacher I have often felt challenged when faced with cases similar to Marta's. How can I teach "relational mathematics" in the face of so many pressures from the school institution (for example, the curriculum to complete or the comparison with the contents covered by colleagues in view of the common tests, for my students and theirs, required by the school)? Is it worth teaching it? How can students experience the transition from instrumental mathematics to relational mathematics? What values of the students can this transition break (see, for example, Doris's statement in paragraph 4)? And what about students who in the future will still find, from other teachers, only instrumental mathematics? Can we be sure that relational mathematics interests and involves all students? Is relational mathematics the means or the end? Do those who propose relational mathematics perhaps have in mind only the onto-epistemic aspects and neglect the axiological and ethical ones? Or perhaps they simply occupy an alternate Axiology? This last point is pertinent to the connection to Anyon (1980) explored above—values imposed by bourgeois interests definitionally exist in conflict with values that center the liberation of the Working Class.

As this entire article suggests for teachers to limit themselves only to onto-epistemic aspects of teaching proposals is to miss Axiological characteristics that profoundly shape onto-epistemology, invisibly circumscribing what seems possible or acceptable. In my experience as a teacher, I have come to the conclusion that, perhaps, we mathematicians have too much faith in the "enchanted" power of mathematics. A teaching proposal made to oppose the spread of instrumental mathematics must consider the values in which students believe, and the ways those values are shaped by coherence and conflict with overarching systems and cultural values. It must consider the relationships within the school institution and the recovery of relationships of responsibility between individuals, first and foremost between the teacher who is the author of the proposal—or the author of a text—and the student.

Concluding Remarks and Questions for Further Research

A historical text is, in some sense, a "place of extreme otherness" due to various characteristics linked to temporal distance (inherent in language, mathematical formalism, rhetorical aspects, etc.). In the experiment illustrated in this article, the chosen passage may seem more mathematically complex than a passage taken from a textbook currently in use. In fact, in just a few lines we note the density of mathematical claims: equivalence between $a^x = y$ and $x = \log_a y$, deduction that $\log 1 = 0$, implicit information about the base, use of integer exponents for illustrating a general property, logarithmic base whose logarithm equals 1, negative logarithms, logarithm of negative numbers. After my decades of work with students, I think this was a central reason for the difficulties encountered by many students in the experiment.

The analysis of Marta's report suggests answers to my research questions as well as directions for further research and analysis. It gives meaning to the theoretical aspects derived from Levinas' thought and referred to the mathematics class. In addition to answering questions regarding students' approach to mathematical texts, this suggests more general reflections regarding students and school mathematics.

The origin of the students' involvement in the interpretation of the passage is an instantiation of an I-Other relation. The relation with the Third Party (the instructional institution through the

teacher as a member of the mathematical community) is manifested in the students' reports; I have focused in particular on that of a “low-achieving” student. The role of Third Party is attributed to people who are bearers and communicators of shared mathematical knowledge. Students' reports look like products aimed at communicating mathematical content, too, but within a different Axiology and concomitant relation of responsibility. In Marta's report there is an incomplete reference to the steps of reasoning exposed by Euler. Her writing of “rules” surfaces an axiology that values solving exercises over understanding per se. I have considered that in the student's experience, the final act of a teaching/learning path is the administration of assessment tests, mainly consisting of a collection of exercises. In Marta's interpretation of the passage, a necessary (although not sufficient) phase of the learning process is lacking, namely the I-Other relation articulated in listening, answerability, and responsibility for the Other. The student has produced a report that complies with the spirit of formal criteria accepted by the Third Party (this said with primary reference to the previous theoretical Levinasian description). She identifies a generally incorrect “rule” which nonetheless enables her to perform some exercises correctly. In this way, she has obtained/constructed the necessary resources to pass an assessment test. From the Third Party, a student can gain benefits such as the attribution of positive votes/judgments: could this make it convenient for her to abandon the possibly onerous phase of responsibility for the Other, by referring directly to the Third Party?⁷ In the experiment illustrated in the present article, this possible outcome is surfaced as concerns a low-achieving student. However, it cannot be excluded that it may also concern other students, i.e. those with “high achievement.”

Let us consider that this outcome may be repeated in all the years in which the student remains in school—it may become recurrent, or even prevalent to the point of becoming a default. Could it produce a “habitus” (Bourdieu's term intended as a form of lasting disposition and propensity to act) in students? In the eyes of students, could the mathematics classroom be a place that has among its characteristics the consent to an incomplete understanding and, however, to obtain the approval of the institution? Is the educational institution aware of this? Is this a flaw in the system, or is this the system working as intended (i.e. should the system be revised, or should it be torn down and replaced)? These are questions that invite further research and require additional reflection.

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

I have been working on the history of mathematics in the context of teaching for years. Introspectively, I can speculate about the reasons for my sustained interest. Perhaps I was decisively captured by the realization that going back in time in search of the origins of mathematical ideas leads to the discovery of the human beings who constructed these ideas. People, and connecting to the human foundation of mathematics, seems a decisive element in my journey. Then my subsequent encounter—rather recent, about ten years ago—with the work of Emmanuel Levinas completed the picture: The role of human beings is fundamental, considered from a philosophical point of view, to an extent that goes beyond the psychological aspects that always have, in my view, contingent elements. In the light of Levinas' thought it seems almost inevitable that I would also consider my relationship with students, and their relationship with the human beings who have worked in mathematics in the past centuries.

⁷ Considered as “onerous” for various possible reasons, e.g. for the fact that it is time consuming. I just want only to mention here that the shortcut of direct reference to the Third Party can be an opportunity that the students feel they have when faced with their own difficulties in mathematics. That is, from the students' point of view, a way to overcome these difficulties would not be the search for understanding, but the search for formal acts aimed at compliance with the Third Party.

A beautiful picture, but one that needs special areas to be told: Areas in which the complexity of the picture can emerge without being thematized, but which appear as a background from which reflections and considerations emerge, sharing the mathematics class as a fixed point of reference. Perhaps this makes the conclusions of what I have written in this paper appear weak from the point of view of hegemonic research in mathematics education. However, I remain open to perspectives, even critical ones, by others who have their own ideas regarding the class, the use of history and, in general, the consideration of the axio-onto-epistemic aspects to which ethics is a guiding criterion for reflection.

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